

An example of how a methodological mistake aggravates erroneous results when only correcting the results and not the method itself

A necessary review of the Reply [Symmetry 8, 24 \(2016\)](#)

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Abstract

Despite correcting their symmetry analysis in Janocha *et al.* (2015) according to some of our comments put forward in [Symmetry 8, 23 \(2016\)](#), their revised method presented in [Symmetry 8, 24 \(2016\)](#) is still incorrect. In fact, even more strange and unrealistic symmetries are now obtained than before the correction. The key problem is that only secondary technical errors were considered for correction, and not the primary methodological mistake itself, which, if properly corrected, would invalidate their approach. Although understood by the Referees, their Reply to our Comment was nevertheless accepted for publication, not because of the expectation to be a proper mathematical correction to their original study, but more because of the sole effort that at least some response in a written form was received.

1. Introduction

In *Section 2* of our Comment (Frewer & Khujadze, 2016) we give a correct approach as how to develop both a consistent and complete Lie-point symmetry analysis for functional-differential equations. This approach is based solely on classical and well-established methods without having to use any new unusual and sophisticated ideas, which, in the end, may even turn out to be inconsistent, as the one originally proposed in Janocha *et al.* (2015) as well as the one also currently proposed in Waławczyk *et al.* (2016).

This report is split in two parts. In the first part (*Section 2*), we will furnish enough evidence that the supposedly new and corrected approach in Waławczyk *et al.* (2016), as presented in *Appendix A*, and, as opposed to the corresponding version in their original study (Janocha *et al.*, 2015), still is and always will be incorrect as long as not *all* of our critical comments have been fully acknowledged. In the second part (*Section 3*), we will give a list of objections on a point-to-point basis, which, in an expected way, will refute all logical fallacies appearing in Waławczyk *et al.* (2016). Ultimately, this particular list makes it apparent that our approach developed in Frewer & Khujadze (2016), which is just based on classical and well-established ideas, has been misinterpreted.

For the sake of a better readability in the following, we will introduce the abbreviations: [A] for the original article by Janocha *et al.* (2015), [C] for our Comment (Frewer & Khujadze, 2016), and [R] for their Reply (Waławczyk *et al.*, 2016).

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2. Evidence that the revised approach in [R] is still incorrect

The current Reply of Janocha *et al.* acknowledges our objections *E.1-E.2* [C, pp.12-15] and were used as a guideline to correct their analysis accordingly. However, for the reader, it does not become clear whether their new achievement in *Appendix A* [R, pp.7-13] should constitute a necessary replacement or only a partial correction to their former study developed in [A], or rather, whether it only should be an optional alternative to it. The purpose of that *Appendix A* is not properly declared to the reader. Also, that an overall different result in the structure of the symmetries is obtained, is not explicitly mentioned, although for the reader it would be vital to know that suddenly a new set of symmetries is obtained [R, p.13], which in their structure strongly differ from the former published symmetries [A, *Theorem 9*, p.1558]. Especially the results for the infinitesimals ξ_x and η_ϕ are fundamentally different; also the result for ξ_t is more general than before.

Yet, despite the corrections done, the new revised analysis given in [R] is still incorrect. Here are three facts that support this statement:

- (a) Our main critique in *Section 1* [C], our discussion *D.3* in *Section 2* [C], and the two basic technical errors *E.3-E.4* revealed in *Section 3* [C], all of them were neither considered nor acknowledged in [R].[†] However, in order to obtain a complete and consistent symmetry analysis for functional-differential equations, in particular for those of the Hopf-type, *all* of our comments have to be taken into account. Instead, only the two other, rather trivial technical issues (*E.1* and *E.2*) were chosen as necessary to formulate a revised version in [R], while the methodological error of their approach was retained. As a consequence, the situation even worsened compared with the results obtained before in [A], e.g., a new, yet more strange and unrealistic symmetries is obtained, which will be examined in (b) below.

To document that the methodological mistake in [A] has not been corrected, we just have to consider *Eq.(8)* in [R], which serves as the basis for their newly proposed approach in *Appendix A* [R, pp.7-13]. First of all, *Eq.(8)* in [R] is not a new independent ansatz, since, as claimed, it has been taken again from the same Master Thesis of D. Janocha from which the erroneous study in [A] resulted in the first place (see also the statement made in *Author Contributions* in [A, p.1563]). Secondly, that the third term on the right-hand side of *Eq.(8)* is manifestly incorrect, can be readily seen when recalling again the basic definition of a functional derivative. According to the line of reasoning in [R], *Eq.(8)* should follow from *Eq.(6)* in the limit of an infinite number of variables y_n . However, when recalling the basic definition of an integral as a sum in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$

$$\int dx f(x) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^N \epsilon f(x_n), \quad (2.1)$$

then the correct limit of the third term in *Eq.(6)* leads to[‡]

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{\Phi}}{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}_n} \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}_n}{\mathcal{D}t} &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty; \epsilon \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^N \epsilon \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{\Phi}}{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}_n/\epsilon} \right) \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}_n/\epsilon}{\mathcal{D}t} = \int d\bar{x} \left(\frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{\Phi}}{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})d\bar{x}} \right) \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})}{\mathcal{D}t} \\ &= \int d\bar{x} \frac{\delta\bar{\Phi}}{\delta\bar{y}(\bar{x})} \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})}{\mathcal{D}t} = \int d\bar{x} \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})}{\mathcal{D}t} \frac{\delta\bar{\Phi}}{\delta\bar{y}(\bar{x})}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

[†]Although objection *E.4* is considered and discussed in [R], our argument has not been fully understood, particularly the part before *Eq.(77)* in [C]. Unfortunately, to substantiate our argument we have not chosen a correct representative example. However, with another choice, we will rectify that. This issue will be discussed in more detail in *Section 3*.

[‡]Also recall [R, *Eq.(1)→(2)*]: $\sum_{n=1}^N U(x_n, t) y_n = \sum_{n=1}^N \epsilon U(x_n, t) y_n / \epsilon \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty; \epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int dx U(x, t) y(x)$.

and not to the incorrect expression as given in Eq.(8), because, obviously

$$d\bar{x} \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})}{\mathcal{D}t} \neq \frac{\mathcal{D}\bar{y}(\bar{x})d\bar{x}}{\mathcal{D}t} \underset{[A],[R]}{=} \frac{\overline{\mathcal{D}y(x)dx}}{\mathcal{D}t}, \quad (2.3)$$

as also confirmed in the conclusion to Eq.(24) vs. Eq.(25) in [R]. Note that for the last line in (2.2), Hopf's defining notation of a functional derivative was used (see [A, p.1539] and also the discussion in [C, p.2]).

Hence, according to our Comment [C] and to the demonstration given above, we can confidently say again, that not only their former original formulation of the total functional variation, as given by Eq.(7) in [R], is wrong, but that also their newly proposed formulation, as given by Eq.(8) and Eq.(24) in [R], is wrong when compared to the corresponding correct formulation of Eq.(25) as constantly used by us in [C]. As was already discussed in detail in E.1-E.2 [C, pp.12-15], please note again that Eq.(7) in [R] is already wrong in the first place, also when making only sole use of the reasoning principle in [A] and [R] that $y(x)dx$ can be assumed as a stand-alone variable.

- (b) The newly determined symmetry in [R, p.13], referring to the group parameter a_2 and not part of the former published symmetry set in [A], is unrealistic in the following sense: When *excluding* the symmetry-breaking constraint of a non-temporal y -field, we have shown in [C] that the viscous Hopf-Burgers equation admits a projective statistical symmetry in the form as derived in [C, Eq.(A27)]. The infinitesimals for this symmetry are given by (in our notation)

$$\xi_t = t^2, \quad \xi_x = t \cdot x, \quad \xi_{y(x)} = 0, \quad \eta_\phi = 0, \quad (2.4)$$

or, in the *new* notation by Janocha *et al.* [R, Eq.(21)], as:

$$\xi_t = t^2, \quad \xi_x = t \cdot x, \quad \xi_{y(x)dx} = \xi_{\gamma(x)}dx = t \cdot y(x)dx, \quad \eta_\phi = 0. \quad (2.5)$$

Now, this symmetry can only be found in the new set of symmetries [R, p.13], if we put $A_2(t) = t^2$, where $A'_2(t) = a_2(t) = 2t$. But, this choice will lead to

$$\xi_t = t^2, \quad \xi_x = 2t \cdot x + 2t \cdot i\nu \int_G y(x')dx', \quad \xi_{y(x)dx} = \xi_{\gamma(x)}dx = 0, \quad \eta_\phi = 0, \quad (2.6)$$

instead of to the correct result (2.5). For $\xi_t = t^2$, it is more than obvious that this new symmetry (2.6) cannot represent the projective statistical symmetry of the Hopf-Burgers equation[†]: (i) The projective symmetry of the underlying deterministic Burgers equation shows no explicit dependence on the viscosity parameter ν , as incorrectly given through ξ_x in (2.6), neither on the deterministic nor on the statistical level. (ii) The result for the infinitesimal $\xi_{y(z)dz}$ in (2.6) should be *non-zero*, when compared to the correct result in (2.5). (iii) When considering the purely inviscid case ($\nu = 0$), we obtain, relative to ξ_t , a by a factor two wrong infinitesimal ξ_x .[‡]

Hence, with their new approach [R, pp.7-13], the authors not only fail to determine the existing (intermediate) projective symmetry of the Hopf-Burgers equation, that has its roots in the underlying deterministic Burgers equation, but also propose in [R, p.13] a new symmetry which evidently is unrealistic and therefore, ultimately, also not to be expected to be observed within a properly performed symmetry analysis, as we will discuss next.

[†]See also Frewer *et al.* (2016) and the references therein.

[‡]Please note that this difference by a factor two in the symmetries constitutes a clear inconsistency in the newly proposed results [R, p.13], and is *not* due to the in the convective term by a factor two differently scaled Burgers equation, as defined in [A, Eq.(6)] and used throughout [A] and [R].

(c) Indeed, the new symmetry in [R], belonging to the group parameter a_2 , is *not* admitted as a symmetry by the governing Hopf-Burgers equation, as wrongly claimed in [R, p.13], neither in the viscous nor in the inviscid case. This can be easily verified by following the same procedure as described in *Appendix A* in our Comment [C, pp.18-21]. Moreover, also the other new, in their words “spurious” symmetry, belonging to the group parameter a_4 and explicitly shown in [R, Eq.(11)], is *not* admitted as a symmetry.[†] Their justification for its existence, namely to positively expect that this spurious symmetry also “follows from the modified method presented by Frewer and Khujadze” [R, p.2], is absurd: Firstly, our approach in [C] is not a modification to the (methodologically wrong) analysis proposed in [A]. Instead, our approach constitutes a complete replacement to theirs. Secondly, our approach does not allow for such a spurious symmetry; its existence simply cannot be confirmed. Hence, also their subsequent concern that “this symmetry was not discussed by Frewer and Khujadze” [R, p.2] is thus meaningless, because how to discuss a symmetry when it does not exist in the first place? Please note again that the above discussion is only based on a symmetry analysis that *excludes* the internal symmetry-breaking constraint of a non-temporal y -field, as it also was still performed throughout in [R, pp.7-13]. Because, if this constraint would be included, the two unrealistic symmetries discussed above would immediately break and thus would not exist anyway (see the final conclusion in [R, p.13]).

3. Refuting all remaining criticisms in [R]

In this section we want to do a point-by-point response to all remaining criticisms outlined in the Reply of Janocha *et al.*:

- (1) We don’t agree that “the analysis proposed by Frewer and Khujadze is based on the method from Refs.[5],[6]” [R, p.1]. Our proposed analysis is solely based on the classical method of Fushchich and Zawistowski when prolonged to functional terms, as we clearly state in the beginning of *Section 2* of our Comment, and not on any method as introduced by Oberlack *et al.* In particular, as their previous developments, cited as *Refs.[5],[6]* in [R], not only (i) show a fundamental shortcoming on their own part (which is discussed in a separate publication in Frewer *et al.* (2016)), but also (ii) do not address the problem of combining implicit and explicit functional dependence as we are facing in our criticism to their approach. The method of Oberlack *et al.* is not the appropriate one to solve such a problem.
- (2) Please note that their claim “The scaling symmetry of Φ (X_7 in Ref.[1]) ... is present also in other methods used to describe stochastic fields ...” [R, p.2] should be interpreted with care. It is true that this symmetry is also present in other statistical descriptions, but as we have shown in another separate publication in Frewer *et al.* (2015), this symmetry is a mere mathematical artefact void of physical meaning. This issue is also discussed at the end of *Section A.3* in the appendix of our Comment [C, p.26].
- (3) Their statement that “such an approach is valid only for ... transformations $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$ ” [R, p.3] and “that the modification of the method proposed by Frewer and Khujadze still accounts for the transformations $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$ only, similar to the method proposed in [1]” [R, p.4], is *not* true. A simple counter-example is, e.g., the temporal scaling symmetry of the inviscid Hopf-Burgers equation (which has its roots in the deterministic

[†]It is only admitted as a symmetry by the *inviscid* Hopf-Burgers equation, i.e. when $\nu = 0$, representing then the statistical version of the temporal scaling symmetry for the deterministic Euler-Burgers equation. For more details, see Frewer *et al.* (2016), where this symmetry is discussed as S_1 in Fourier space.

formulation of the Burgers equation — see Frewer *et al.* (2016), where this symmetry is discussed as S_1 in Fourier space)

$$\bar{t} = e^\varepsilon t, \quad \bar{x} = x, \quad \bar{y}(\bar{x}) = e^\varepsilon y(x), \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (3.1)$$

where the auxiliary field y does *not* transform frame-indifferently $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$,[†] as claimed and exclusively used in [R, pp.3-4]. The transformation (3.1) is perfectly in accord with our developed differential infinitesimal [C, Eq.(49)], which for (3.1) gives the correct result: $\zeta_{;y(x)} = -\Phi_{;y(x)}$. Hence, our approach does not account for frame-indifferent transformations $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$ only, as wrongly claimed in [R].

For us it is unclear how this incorrect statement came about, or how it can be concluded from its preceding discussion in [R], based on the Eqs.(1)-(7). We don't see any reasonable indication of how the expansion in [R, Eq.(4)] can lead to such a statement that only transformations of the (strong) form $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$ are allowed, in particular as there is also no need for such an expansion to perform a consistent symmetry analysis, which we already clearly stated in our Comment as a separate remark [C, p.13].

- (4) Their claim that the inequality of Eq.(10) in [R] proves an inconsistency of our approach, is not justified. Our so-called “Galilei-type” transformation $\langle S_2 \rangle$ given in [C, Eq.(A41)], where U has been broken to transform invariantly ($\bar{U} = U$), only shows the relation

$$\Phi = \bar{\Phi} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \langle e^{i \int U(x,t)y(x)dx} \rangle = \langle e^{i \int \bar{U}(\bar{x},\bar{t})\bar{y}(\bar{x})d\bar{x}} \rangle, \quad (3.2)$$

and *not* the relation

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial \bar{\Phi}}{\partial \bar{t}} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \\ \left\langle e^{i \int U(x,t)y(x)dx} \int \frac{\partial U(x,t)}{\partial t} y(x) dx \right\rangle &= \left\langle e^{i \int \bar{U}(\bar{x},\bar{t})\bar{y}(\bar{x})d\bar{x}} \int \frac{\partial \bar{U}(\bar{x},\bar{t})}{\partial \bar{t}} \bar{y}(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} \right\rangle, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.3)$$

as the “proof” via Eq.(10) in [R] tries to suggest, which obviously already by the very nature of this transformation $\langle S_2 \rangle$ [C, Eq.(A41)]

$$\bar{t} = t, \quad \bar{x} = x + ct, \quad \bar{y}(\bar{x}) = y(x), \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (3.4)$$

cannot be satisfied, simply because $\partial_t \neq \partial_{\bar{t}}$. Hence, the inequality $\partial_t \Phi \neq \partial_{\bar{t}} \bar{\Phi}$ is a natural property of this transformation (3.4), *independent* of how the deterministic velocity field U transforms, and therefore, ultimately, does not prove anything if this inequality holds, in particular not that our approach is faulty. Trivially, note that (3.3) can only hold if $c = 0$; but why should we make this choice? At this stage, there is no reason for it!

- (5) We cannot confirm that “there is an additional, spurious symmetry, which can be obtained with the proposal of Frewer and Khujadze” [R, p.4]. The Hopf-Burgers equation does *not* admit this transformation of Eq.(11) in [R] as an intermediate symmetry. Please also see the discussion (c) given in Section 2.
- (6) Their claim that “We do not agree with the objection raised by Frewer and Khujadze in Paragraph E.4” [R, p.4], is based on two critical assumptions: **(A)** All multi-point functions, to all orders, always have to converge *uniformly* if one of the coordinates tend to infinity, and **(B)** the characteristic functional itself always has to be analytic.

[†]Note that the strong requirement of an invariant function $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = \bar{y}(x)$ is to be distinguished from the weaker requirement of an invariant transformation $\bar{y}(\bar{x}) = y(x)$ regarding the variable y .

Let us first discuss the former assumption (A): To only allow for uniform convergence in *all* multi-point correlations is a strong assumption, in view of the fact that due to intermittency effects in the fluctuations the topology of the multi-point functions becomes more rich and complex as the number of points (dimensional order) increases. But exactly this assumption is needed to make the conclusion to Eq.(17) in [R], namely that the limit and integration processes can always be interchanged to all orders

$$\begin{aligned}
\left. \frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta y(x_i)} \right|_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} & \stackrel{(I)}{=} \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} f_1(x_i, t) + \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} \int 2f_2(x_i, x, t)y(x)dx \\
& + \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} \int 3f_3(x_i, x, x', t)y(x)y(x')dxdx' + \dots \\
& \stackrel{(II)}{=} \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} f_1(x_i, t) + \int 2 \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} f_2(x_i, x, t)y(x)dx \\
& + \int 3 \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} f_3(x_i, x, x', t)y(x)y(x')dxdx' + \dots \quad (3.5)
\end{aligned}$$

where the integrands f_n are connected to the multi-point functions as[†]

$$f_n(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = \frac{1}{n!} \frac{\delta^n \Phi}{\delta y(x_1) \cdots \delta y(x_n)} \Big|_{y=0} = \frac{i^n}{n!} \langle U^t(x_1) \cdots U^t(x_n) \rangle. \quad (3.6)$$

Unfortunately, in our Comment [C, Eq.(77)] we have chosen an incorrect example for a simple representable Hopf-functional to demonstrate that the above procedure (3.5), namely in going from (I) to (II), cannot always be assumed. A drawback which, however, can be easily overcome when re-defining the arbitrary function g in Eq.(77) accordingly. Instead of considering only a function of the form $g = g(x'', x''')$, we now parametrically re-define this function such that it also includes the third integration coordinate x' in the following way:

$$g(x'', x''') \mapsto g_{x'}(x'', x''') \stackrel{e.g.}{=} x'^2 \cdot \widehat{g}(x' \cdot x'', x' \cdot x'''), \quad (3.7)$$

where \widehat{g} is any two-dimensional real and symmetric scalar function decaying sufficiently fast at space infinity $\|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty$, such that $g_{x'}$ decays, too. Replacing g by $g_{x'}$ in Eq.(77), we then obtain the iterative result (shown here explicitly only up to fourth moment)

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, t) &= i f(t) e^{-\lambda x_1^2}, \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, t) &= \frac{i^2}{2!} f(t)^2 e^{-\lambda(x_1^2 + x_2^2)}, \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3, t) &= \frac{i^3}{3!} f(t)^3 e^{-\lambda(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)} \\
&+ \frac{2i}{3!} f(t) \left(g_{x_1}(x_2, x_3) + g_{x_2}(x_1, x_3) + g_{x_3}(x_1, x_2) \right), \\
f_4(x_1, \dots, x_4, t) &= \frac{i^4}{4!} f(t)^4 e^{-\lambda(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2)} \\
&+ \frac{2i^2}{4!} f(t)^2 e^{-\lambda x_1^2} \left(g_{x_2}(x_3, x_4) + g_{x_3}(x_2, x_4) + g_{x_4}(x_2, x_3) \right) \\
&+ \frac{2i^2}{4!} f(t)^2 e^{-\lambda x_2^2} \left(g_{x_1}(x_3, x_4) + g_{x_3}(x_1, x_4) + g_{x_4}(x_1, x_3) \right) \\
&+ \frac{2i^2}{4!} f(t)^2 e^{-\lambda x_3^2} \left(g_{x_1}(x_2, x_4) + g_{x_2}(x_1, x_4) + g_{x_4}(x_1, x_2) \right) \\
&+ \frac{2i^2}{4!} f(t)^2 e^{-\lambda x_4^2} \left(g_{x_1}(x_2, x_3) + g_{x_2}(x_1, x_3) + g_{x_3}(x_1, x_2) \right).
\end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.8)$$

[†]Note that the expression of Eq.(16) in [R] contains a misprint: The pre-factor is not correct; it has to be replaced by the above expression (3.6).

Now, when choosing, for example, the infinitely smooth and analytic specification

$$g_x(x', x'') = x^2 \cdot \left(e^{-x^4(x'^4+x''^4)} - e^{-x^2(x'^2+x''^2)} \right), \quad y(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}, \quad (3.9)$$

which is a valid specification, since g_x obeys all constraints of Equation (3.7) and y that of any arbitrary (asymptotically) decaying function, then, for $\lambda > 0$, equality (I) in (3.5) evaluates to a non-zero value[†]

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta y(x_i)} \right|_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} &= if(t) \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} \int g_{x_i}(x, x') y(x) y(x') dx dx' + \dots \\ &= if(t) \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} \left[\left(x_i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz \frac{e^{-x_i^4 \cdot z^4}}{\sqrt{1+z^2}} \right)^2 - \left(x_i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz \frac{e^{-x_i^2 \cdot z^2}}{\sqrt{1+z^2}} \right)^2 \right] + \dots \\ &= if(t) \left(\frac{1}{4} \Gamma(1/4)^2 - \pi \right) + \text{higher-order terms} \neq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

while equality (II) in (3.5) evaluates to zero[‡] for all orders, meaning that the limit and integration processes may not be interchanged. Hence, the correct result is given by (I) and not by the zero-result (II), as generally claimed in [R], simply because when evaluating an expression as

$$\left. \frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta y(x_i)} \right|_{x_i \rightarrow \infty}, \quad (3.11)$$

the asymptotic limit always has to be taken after the derivative operation, i.e., this limit always has to be taken as the final operation. Note that when including all orders in the infinite series of (3.10), then the first functional derivative evaluated at space infinity will converge to

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta y(x_i)} \right|_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} &= if(t) \Phi \lim_{x_i \rightarrow \infty} \int g_{x_i}(x, x') y(x) y(x') dx dx' \\ &= if(t) \Phi \left(\frac{1}{4} \Gamma(1/4)^2 - \pi \right) \neq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

which can be easily obtained by just evaluating the functional derivative directly without unnecessarily expanding it first into a Taylor series. The non-zero result (3.12) thus restores our result Eq.(84), and therefore also our objection E.4 in [C, pp.16-17], in particular as our classical functional symmetry-approach put forward in [C, Section 2] does not need to make this strong and unnecessary assumption of uniform convergence for all multi-point moments to all orders, as implicitly assumed in [A] and [R].

Let us now discuss the second critical assumption (B): To assume that the characteristic functional $\Phi = \Phi(t, y(x'))$ can always be represented as a power series, as formulated in [R, Eq.(15)], is problematic on two counts: (i) It is unclear in how far the functional power series always converges to the necessary third constraint $|\Phi| \leq 1$, as previously defined in [A, p.1559], and (ii) not every functional Φ is an analytic function in the auxiliary field y , in order to always justify such an expansion. In this regard, it should be mentioned that also non-analytical characteristic functionals are valid functionals which can generate well-defined statistical moments. This is in particular the case, when any analytical functional is multiplicatively extended by a non-analytic part.

[†]Note that for the particular specification (3.9), equality (I) in (3.5) gives different non-zero contributions for all $f_{n \geq 3}$ -integrals ($n \in \mathbb{N}$). The explicit evaluation (3.10) only shows the lowest order result for $n = 3$.

[‡]Due to that $g_x(x', x'')$ in (3.9) converges *pointwise* to zero if one of the coordinates tend to infinity.

For example, when considering the infinitely smooth but *non-analytic* Hopf-functional

$$\Phi(t, y(x')) = \widehat{\Phi}(t, y(x')) \cdot e^{i\Psi(y(x')) \int dx'' y(x'')}, \quad (3.13)$$

where $\widehat{\Phi}$ is any *analytic* part that generates asymptotically decaying moments and satisfies the usual internal Hopf-constraints [A, p.1559]

$$\widehat{\Phi}^*(t, y(x')) = \widehat{\Phi}(t, -y(x')), \quad \widehat{\Phi}(t, 0) = 1, \quad |\widehat{\Phi}(t, y(x'))| \leq 1, \quad (3.14)$$

followed by some infinitely smooth but *non-analytic* real-valued functional Ψ with the necessary properties $\Psi(-y) = \Psi(y)$ and $\Psi(0) = 0$, e.g.,

$$\Psi(y(x')) = e^{-\frac{1}{\lambda^2}} \Big|_{\lambda = \int dx' y(x')}, \quad (3.15)$$

then the functional (3.13) will obviously lead to a *non-zero* derivative when just evaluated at the infinite far point only

$$\frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta y(x)} \Big|_{x=\pm\infty} = \frac{\Phi}{\widehat{\Phi}} \left[\underbrace{\frac{\delta\widehat{\Phi}}{\delta y(x)} \Big|_{x=\pm\infty}}_{\substack{=0, \text{ if uniform convergent} \\ \neq 0, \text{ if non-uniform convergent}}} + \widehat{\Phi} \cdot \left(i \underbrace{\frac{\delta\Psi}{\delta y(x)} \Big|_{x=\pm\infty}}_{\substack{\neq 0, \\ \text{if } y \neq 0}} \int dx'' y(x'') + i\Psi \right) \right] \neq 0, \quad (3.16)$$

which therefore serves as another example against the strong argument in [A] and [R] that the functional derivatives are always zero when a spatial variable tends to infinity. Because, although the functional (3.13) with (3.15) is non-analytic, the multi-point correlations are nevertheless all well defined

$$\langle U^t(x_1) \cdots U^t(x_n) \rangle = \frac{1}{i^n} \Phi_{,y(x_1)\dots y(x_n)} \Big|_{y=0} = \frac{1}{i^n} \widehat{\Phi}_{,y(x_1)\dots y(x_n)} \Big|_{y=0}, \quad (3.17)$$

and, due to the assumption that the analytic functional $\widehat{\Phi}$ generates asymptotically decaying moments, they also are all vanishing at the infinite far point as required:

$$\langle U^t(x_1) \cdots U^t(x_n) \rangle \Big|_{\|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty} = \frac{1}{i^n} \widehat{\Phi}_{,y(x_1)\dots y(x_n)} \Big|_{y=0, \|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty} = 0. \quad (3.18)$$

Conclusion: Hence, when restricting the analysis only to those solutions Φ of the Hopf-Burgers equation, which are analytic and which only generate uniform converging statistical moments, as was unnecessarily done throughout in [A] and [R], will inevitably result into a very narrow and restricted symmetry analysis, where one runs the high risk of not capturing all symmetries. In clear contrast, of course, to our proposed approach in [C], where such strong assumptions on the dependent variable Φ in the Hopf-Burgers equation are not needed.

- (7) Their claim that “The error of Frewer and Khujadze becomes particularly apparent, as they introduce their result for $\xi_{y(x)} = 0$ into our formula for $\zeta_{y(x)}$ ” [R, p.5], ignores the fact that one obtains the result $\zeta_{y(x)} = 0$ indeed, if and only if one strictly follows the notation as defined and presented in their published article [A], in particular as denoted in *Definition 5* along with *Eq.(11)*, is misleading to a reader. Hence, to obtain the incorrect result $\zeta_{y(x)} = 0$ is not an “error”, but only the logical consequence of a misleading notation in [A], as we also clearly state in [C, p.11].

- (8) Their conclusion that “ Φ is a functional of two function spaces U and y if both of them are to be transformed” [R, p.6], is absurd. To understand why, let us repeat their argument to this conclusion. The baseline of the argument is the definition of the characteristic functional

$$\Phi(y(x), t) = \langle e^{i \int U(x,t)y(x)dx} \rangle, \quad (3.19)$$

and the fact that for the intermediate projective symmetry, as determined in our approach in [C], both y and Φ transform invariantly, while the coordinates, however, transform non-invariantly as [R, Eq.(26)]:

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{1 - t\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{x} = \frac{x}{1 - t\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{y}(\bar{x}) = y(x), \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi. \quad (3.20)$$

As correctly stated in [R, Eq.(27)], namely in order to maintain consistency for the invariant transformation $\Phi = \bar{\Phi}$

$$\langle e^{i \int U(x,t)y(x)dx} \rangle = \langle e^{i \int \bar{U}(\bar{x},\bar{t})\bar{y}(\bar{x})d\bar{x}} \rangle = \langle e^{i \int \bar{U}(\bar{x},\bar{t})y(x)\frac{dx}{1-t\varepsilon}} \rangle, \quad (3.21)$$

the velocity field U then has to transform as

$$\bar{U}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = (1 - t\varepsilon)U(x, t). \quad (3.22)$$

But, then to conclude that the functional Φ (3.19) must depend on y and U for the only reason that U undergoes a transformational change, is definitely wrong. It simply has been overlooked that the averaging process in the characteristic functional (3.19) is further defined as a path integral over a probability density functional f , exactly as already formulated in their original study [A, p.1538]

$$\Phi(y(x), t) = \int f(U(x), t) e^{i \int U(x)y(x)dx} d[U(x)], \quad (3.23)$$

where f is the probability density functional and $d[U(x)]$ the functional volume element over an ensemble of all possible spatial velocity fields $U(x)$. This means that U is a closed integration variable (dummy variable) which cannot appear anymore on the left-hand side of (3.23), and this, of course, independent of how U transforms. Hence, the characteristic functional Φ cannot depend on U , as misleadingly and wrongly stated in [R, Eq.(27)]. Obviously, this also provides the reason of why this wrong functional dependence “was not accounted for in the analysis of Frewer and Khujadze” [R, p.6]. That the reasoning in [R, p.6] is wrong *per se* can also be readily seen when reducing the above setting to the following situation: Since (3.23) operates as a functional Fourier transform, let’s reduce it representatively to the following usual 1D Fourier transform

$$\varphi(k, t) = \int u(x, t) e^{ikx} dx, \quad (3.24)$$

where φ is the corresponding Fourier-field of the 1D velocity field u , and as a representative transformation which more or less mimics (3.20), let’s choose, for example, the following similar transformation:

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{1 - t\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{k} = \frac{k}{1 - t\varepsilon}, \quad \bar{\varphi}(\bar{k}, \bar{t}) = \varphi(k, t). \quad (3.25)$$

As before in (3.21), in order to maintain consistency for the given invariant transformation $\varphi = \bar{\varphi}$

$$\int u(x, t) e^{ikx} dx = \int \bar{u}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) e^{i\bar{k}\bar{x}} d\bar{x} = \int \bar{u}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) e^{i\frac{k}{1-t\varepsilon}\bar{x}} d\bar{x}, \quad (3.26)$$

the variables x and u consequently have to transform as

$$\bar{x} = (1 - t\varepsilon)x, \quad \bar{u}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = \frac{u(x, t)}{1 - t\varepsilon}. \quad (3.27)$$

But now, to conclude that the Fourier-field φ (3.24) must be a function of k and x , only because x undergoes a transformational change, is obviously wrong: The variables k and x are complementary variables, for which, obviously, the Fourier transform φ cannot collectively depend on, and that, of course, irrespective of whether one, or both variables are transformed or not.

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